
INNOVATION STRATEGIES AND SALES PERFORMANCE OF FOOD AND BEVERAGES FIRMS IN AKWA IBOM STATE

Anthony Bassey Orok

Department of Marketing, University of Calabar, Calabar

anthonyorok@gmail.com

Patience Sunday Odum

Department of Marketing, University of Uyo, Uyo

odumpatience@mail.com

Martin Ikechukwu Kanu

Department of Marketing, University of Uyo, Uyo

martinolifted@gmail.com

Abstract

The researchers critically examined innovation strategy and sale performance of food and beverages firms in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The main objective of the study was to examine the influence of innovation strategies on sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State. The researcher utilized a survey design as the primary research approach. The study was carried out in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, and a structured questionnaire was used as the main data collection tool. 296 staffs across the different food and beverages firm were the respondent. The data from the field was analyzed using simple linear regression. The result revealed a significant influence of innovation strategies dimensions and sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State. The researcher concluded that marketing innovation strategy and process innovation strategy are key element of innovation strategies that influences sales performance in the food and beverages companies and further remanded that Companies that have not been using marketing innovation and process innovation strategy to a large extent should do so in order to be competitive and enhance their sales performance, also that more attention should be paid to emerging and modern technology as the world is bringing up new ways of doing almost everything.

Keywords: innovation, strategy, sale performance, food and beverages firms.

INTRODUCTION

The interconnectedness between innovation and performance or growth in the business world has long been of great interest to marketers. The general opinion is that innovation is among the key determinants of competitive advantage, thus contributing to the ability of firms to grow and gain profit, market shares, and sales volume. An innovation strategy is a plan aimed at increasing market share or profits through the development of new products and services. When viewed from the jobs-to-be-done perspective, an effective strategy involves identifying the right job executor, job, and market segment to target in order to achieve maximum growth. Additionally, it focuses on addressing unmet customer needs to enhance their ability to complete a task more effectively (Al-Battaineh, 2018). Regardless of the specific innovation strategy a company adopts, the immediate motivation could stem from factors such as enhancing product performance, improving productivity, or reducing production costs. The underlying motivation, however, is likely to be the desire to maintain or enhance competitive advantage in either existing or new markets (Alkalouti *et al.*, 2020).

Every organization aims to boost its sales performance, expand market share, increase sales volume, and maximize profits. According to Christian and Awaji-ima (2024), sales performance reflects the degree to which an organization progresses in its selling activities. This underscores the importance of improving sales performance for the survival of beverage companies. Etuk *et al.*, (2021) defined marketing performance as the effectiveness and efficiency of a business's marketing activities in achieving market-related objectives, such as growth, revenue, market share, and sales volume. To achieve robust turnover, sales volume, and market share, particularly in Small and Medium Enterprises, marketers can rely on well-established and effective e-marketing strategies. Gakii and Maina (2019) also suggested that in a competitive environment, businesses have been able to improve their sales performance, market share, and profitability by adopting modern strategies.

Statement of Problem

The major challenge facing food and beverage companies in Akwa Ibom State is how to enhance their sales performance to remain competitive in the industry. Many of these companies struggle to compete effectively with larger firms, primarily due to a lack of innovation, as noted by the researcher. Some scholars argue that product innovation can improve a company's market competitiveness by boosting customer patronage, which, in turn, positively affects sales performance. While both theoretical and empirical studies suggest that innovation plays a significant role in improving sales performance, most of the existing research on innovation and firm performance does not specifically address food and beverage companies in Akwa Ibom State. This creates a gap in the literature that this study seeks to fill. Thus, the purpose of this research is to explore the relationship between innovation strategies and sales performance in food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the influence of innovation strategies on sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.

The specific objectives were to:

- i. Ascertain the influence of marketing innovation strategy on sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.

- ii. Examine the effect of process innovation strategy on sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Hypotheses

- i. H_{01} : Marketing innovation strategy has no influence on sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. H_{02} : Process innovation strategy does not affect sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

- i. Does marketing innovation strategy influences sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. Does Process innovation strategy influences sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Overview of Innovation Strategies

Innovations have been studied from many different dimensions such as economics, business, technology, finance and management. The prevalent discussion among practitioners of innovation has created many approaches to conceptualize innovation. Innovation can be referred to as an act of introducing something new (process of innovation); or something introduced newly (Al-Battaineh, 2018). Tidd and Bessant (2018) opined that Innovative strategies are a set of deliberate, purposeful, and systematic actions designed to stimulate and drive innovation throughout an organization, enabling it to adapt to changing market conditions and sustain growth. This definition highlights the purposeful and systematic nature of innovative strategies, emphasizing their role in enabling adaptation and growth. Canh *et al.* (2019) further stated that innovative strategies refer to the approaches and methods that organizations use to foster and implement innovation within their operations, goods, or services. These strategies are aimed at encouraging creative thinking, generate new ideas, and ultimately drive business growth and competitive advantage.

Wolf *et al.*, (2021) summarized that innovation strategy is a scope of actions for all innovative procedures in an organization which includes strategic goals and guidelines which have the vision to develop innovation. Innovation strategies can be a simple one, where firms focus to introduce only one type of Schumpeterian innovations (i.e. product, process, market or technology) at a time, or the strategy can be a multifaceted one, where firms combine numerous types of simple strategies at a time.

Dimensions of Innovation Strategies

Market innovation strategy

This strategy focuses on identifying and addressing the most important needs of a particular market and developing innovations that cater to those needs (Corniani, 2008). A commonly used approach is the pull strategy, which centers on customer needs. By conducting thorough customer surveys, a company seeks to gather insights into the most critical customer demands. Once these needs are understood, an innovation is created to align with the identified needs.

Market innovation involves adjusting the market mix and selecting markets to align with customer purchasing preferences (Kenea, 2020). Ongoing market innovation is essential for businesses, as advanced marketing tools, especially those available online, allow competitors to quickly reach potential customers globally. Market innovation plays a crucial role in addressing market demands and seizing market opportunities (Rodriguez *et al.*, 2004). In this context, any market innovation must be focused on meeting customer needs and ensuring customer satisfaction.

Process Innovation Strategy

Process innovation focuses on reengineering and enhancing a company's internal operations and processes. This includes various aspects of a firm's functions, such as technical design, research and development, manufacturing, management, and commercial activities (Freeman, 2004). It involves the creation or improvement of techniques, processes, or systems (Azadegan, Napshin, & Oke, 2013). In the context of production, process innovation refers to the development of new or enhanced methods, tools, devices, and knowledge used in manufacturing a product (Azadegan, Napshin, & Oke, 2013). Process innovation is crucial for the manufacturing industry, as it represents a firm's primary competitive advantage and distinctive competence.

Although new products are often the visible outcomes of market innovation, process innovation also plays a critical strategic role. It can be viewed as the introduction of new elements into a company's production process. Achieving marketing performance often requires redefining operational processes and incorporating innovative technologies. According to Maier (2014a), process innovation involves adopting innovations in key business processes, which help reduce costs or production time for goods and services (Maier, 2014a).

Process innovation can be categorized as follows:

- **Technology flow innovations:** These focus on improving the flow of operations and their connections. Examples include automating assembly lines in the automotive industry, replacing milling processes, or linking numerically controlled machines with design systems.
- **Manufacturing process innovations:** These innovations fundamentally change how manufacturing is done, such as the float glass manufacturing process, Tetrapak packaging, or word processing software.
- **Incremental innovations:** These improve outcomes without requiring new knowledge, such as Moore's law in computer science or reducing coke consumption in furnaces.

OVERVIEW OF SALES PERFORMANCE

Sales performance refers to the assessment of the sales generated by business activities, particularly those carried out by individual sales representatives, as described by O'Sullivan and Abela (2007). It measures how effectively a company advances in its marketing efforts. Sales involve the process of exchanging products and services for money or other compensation, initiated and completed by the seller, who owns the goods. The process begins with an agreement for acquisition, followed by the transfer of ownership and

price settlement. A sale is considered complete once the payment is made or becomes obligatory (Anuradha and Vijai, 2011). The sales department plays a crucial role in the growth of any organization, with the aim of increasing interactions between potential customers and the company. This is achieved through various promotional strategies, including advertising, sales promotions, publicity, public relations, the development of new sales channels, and the introduction of new products, among others. It primarily involves the interactions between customers, the sales facility, and the sales representatives. Etuk *et al.*, (2021) opined measuring sales performance enables businesses to adjust their marketing strategies, enhance their competitive advantage, and stay ahead of their competitors' strategies. By assessing a company's performance, marketers can develop new strategies, boost revenue, and effectively achieve their business objectives (Eke, 2022).

Figure1: Conceptual Framework on innovation strategies on sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.

Source: Researchers' Model (2024)

Theoretical Framework

Innovation Diffusion Theory

The Innovation Diffusion Theory, developed by Rogers (1983), explains individuals' willingness to adopt new technologies as a way to perform traditional tasks (Simon and Senaji, 2016). The primary motivator for adopting modern technology is the perceived relative advantage it offers. This theory focuses on how technological innovations are applied and how both individuals and businesses use modern technology to enhance their operations. Olannyei *et al.* (2017) highlighted that the theory describes how individuals and organizations accept technology as a means to improve their traditional operations. Essentially, it addresses the intention to adopt modern technology to perform tasks more

efficiently. The theory is particularly useful for understanding the motives behind product innovation in informal sectors. It suggests that food and beverage SMEs adopt technology to gain a competitive edge over larger competitors. According to Idowu *et al.*, (2016), these SMEs recognize the benefits of incorporating modern technologies, such as Information and Communication Technology (ICT), as a way to enhance their competitiveness. This has led to the development of new production techniques that allow them to create high-quality products. With the use of technology, SMEs are able to manufacture and deliver quality products to their customers (Simon & Senaji, 2016).

The Innovation Diffusion Theory is relevant to this study because it supports the idea that food and beverage firms can leverage technology to innovate their products. The theory illustrates how modern technology enables these firms to initiate product innovations that improve their market competitiveness. By offering innovative products, food and beverage companies can better satisfy their customers, retain them for longer periods, and attract new customers.

Empirical Review

Shih (2018) conducted a study on the determinants of radical innovation and performance in enterprises in the USA. The main aim of the study was to explore the factors influencing radical innovation and performance in American businesses. A quantitative research approach and a descriptive survey design were used, with data collected from managers in 86 cultural and creative organizations through structured questionnaires. The analysis was performed using regression methods. The findings revealed that entrepreneurial and market orientation were key factors facilitating the adoption of radical innovation. Additionally, the study found that brand advantage significantly impacts firm performance after implementing radical innovation.

Muita (2013) explored innovation strategies and competitive advantage within Kenya's telecommunications industry. The study aimed to investigate the relationship between innovation strategies and competitive advantage in the telecommunications sector in Kenya. A descriptive survey design was used, with data collected via structured questionnaires. Various data analysis methods, including percentage and frequency analysis, mean, standard deviation, bar and pie charts, and SPSS version 21.0, were applied. The results indicated that most innovation strategies employed by telecom companies were designed to meet customer needs. The study also found that technological innovation and research played a significant role in enhancing the competitiveness of these companies.

Ifekanandu and Renner (2024) examined innovation strategies and sales performance in food and beverage firms in Rivers State. The study focused on understanding the relationship between innovation strategies and sales performance in this sector. A descriptive survey design was used, with a quantitative approach and data collected from 25 food and beverage firms in the region. The study used a census approach, targeting managerial staff, with questionnaires distributed to 100 respondents. Reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, and both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis, including the Spearman Rank Order Correlation Technique to test hypotheses. The results showed a significant relationship between innovation strategies and sales performance. The study concluded that innovation strategies are strong predictors of sales performance, and recommended that firms experiencing low sales should focus on incremental innovations and adopt radical innovation strategies to attract more customers and improve sales.

Kenea (2020) researched the role of innovation strategies in enhancing organizational performance and productivity, focusing on Heineken's beverage industry in Ethiopia. The study aimed to examine how innovation strategies impact firm performance and productivity. A cross-sectional survey design was employed, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods, including self-administered questionnaires and key informant interviews. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics for the quantitative data and thematic analysis for the qualitative data. The results revealed that innovation strategies were not fully effective across all areas (process, marketing, product, and firm performance). It was found that the current innovation strategy was not helping the organization to improve productivity or meet its performance goals. The study concluded that the organization had not fully implemented the necessary steps to maintain effective innovation strategies. The researcher recommended greater involvement of all stakeholders in establishing and maintaining effective innovation systems to achieve organizational objectives.

Al-Battaineh (2018) conducted a study on the effect of innovation strategies on the functional performance of SMEs in Hassan Industrial City. The objective was to assess how innovation strategies affect the functional performance of SMEs in the city. The study used a sample of 160 questionnaires distributed to managers across three management levels in 20 SMEs, with a response rate of 89%. The results showed that product innovation, process innovation, and management innovation had a significant positive impact on performance, while marketing management did not. The researcher recommended that top management focus on innovative methods for managing employees and organizational processes, ensure that the organizational message aligns with its objectives, and offer both formal and informal training programs to foster creativity among employees.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher adopted survey design as the main research design. This is because survey design allows information to be gathered from a sample of people or organizations by the use of questionnaire.

Study Area

Uyo which is the capital of Akwa Ibom State in the South-South region of Nigeria was adopted as the study area. The proximity of the Area of study to the researcher eased the collection of needed data within the time frame of the study.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of all the staffs that were encountered at the major food beverages vendors at the time of this study. This was irrespective of the demographic variables or social status of the respondents. Since it was not possible to have a clear figure of staffs in this establishment, the population of the study was treated as infinite.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size of this research was determined using the Top-man Formula for infinite population. The adoption of this Formula is to enable us get a sample size for the study which has an unknown population record of daily customers.

Thus, to arrive at an appropriate sample size for the study, a pilot study was carried out, using the research questionnaire on 20 selected customers that were encountered by the

researcher at the super market. The strongly agree and agree responses to the questions allowed the researcher to generate values for 'P' (positive). On the other hand the strongly disagree and disagree responses allowed the researcher to generate values for 'Q' (negative), for the Top-man formula. To determine the sample size, the formula was applied as follows;

$$n = \frac{z^2(p \times q)}{e^2}$$

Where;

- n = required sample size
z = the value of Z-score associated with the degree of confidence i.e. 95% confidence level, being 1.96 from the Z-score table.
p = the percentage of positive response expressed as decimal
q = (p-1) the percentage of negative response expressed as decimal
e = Acceptable tolerance level of error (stated in percentage points)

Thus;

- Z = 1.96^2 i.e. 3.8416
p = 22 i.e. 0.22
q = 8 i.e. 0.08
 e^2 = 0.05^2 i.e. 0.0025

$$n = \frac{3.8416 (0.22 \times 0.08)}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 (0.176)}{0.0025} = \frac{0.67612384}{0.0025} = 270.45 \text{ i.e. } 271$$

Sampling Techniques

Purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting the super markets and respondents for this study. This sampling technique was adopted due to the need to access the type of information and data needed for this study from the target respondent.

Sources of Data

The main source of data for this study was primary data. This primary data was collected directly from the staffs at the different food and beverages establishment.

Data Analysis Techniques

Simple linear regression analysis was used to examine the extent of the relationship that exists between the predictor variables and the criterion variable. The four hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Test of Hypothesis

H₀₁: Marketing innovation strategy has no influence on sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 1. Summary of Simple Regression Showing the Relationship between marketing innovation and sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.

	B₁	SE	B₂	t-value	Significant (2 tailed)
Constant	5.911	0.641	-	9.215	0.000
Marketing innovation strategy	0.355	0.042	0.408	8.517	0.000

Dependent variable: sales performance
 R = 0.408^a
 R² = 0.166
 Adjusted R-square = 0.164
 Std. Error of estimate = 1.63315
 F = 72.533

Significance = 0.000

*significantly related at 5% (p<0.05). B₁= unstandardized beta, B₂= standardized beta, SE= standard error.

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024)

Table 1 shows R² of 0.166 which means that the independent variable (Marketing innovation strategy) accounted for 16.6% of the variation in sales performance. In addition, the significant F-ratio at F = 72.533, p < 0.000 suggest that the results of the regression model could not have occurred by chance and that the independent variables significantly predicted the dependent variable.

To assess the place of the independent variable in determining the level of change in the dependent variable, the beta coefficients for the variable; Marketing innovation strategy had statistically significant standardized coefficient of $\beta = 0.355$, Sig = 0.000, showing a positive significant influence on sales performance. This finding can be interpreted that every 1-unit change in marketing innovation strategy will lead to 0.355 change in sales performance. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 (p=0.000<0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected

H₀₂: Process innovation strategy does not affect sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 2. Summary of Simple Regression Showing the Relationship between Process innovation strategy and sales performance

	B₁	SE	B₂	t-value	Significant (2 tailed)
Constant	5.398	0.645	-	8.370	0.000
Process innovation strategy	0.395	0.043	0.437	9.270	0.000

Dependent variable: Sales performance
 R = 0.437^a
 R² = 0.191
 Adjusted R-square = 0.189
 Std. Error of estimate = 1.60866
 F = 85.926

Significance = 0.000

*significantly related at 5% (p<0.05). B₁= unstandardized beta, B₂= standardized beta, SE= standard error.

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024)

Table 2 shows R^2 of 0.191 which means that the independent variable (Process innovation strategy) accounted for 19.1% of the variation in sales performance. In addition, the significant F-ratio at $F = 85.926$, $p < 0.000$ suggest that the results of the regression model could not have occurred by chance and that the independent variables significantly predicted the dependent variable.

To assess the standing of the independent variable in determining the degree of change in the dependent variable, the beta coefficients for the variable; Process innovation strategy had statistically significant standardized coefficient of $\beta = 0.395$, $\text{Sig} = 0.000$, showing a positive significant influence on sales performance. This finding can be deduced that every 1-unit change in process innovation strategy will lead to 0.395 change in sales performance. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 ($p=0.000 < 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected.

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary

This study was an attempt to examine the influence of innovation strategies on sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.

1. The first null hypothesis stated that marketing innovation strategy has no influence on sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State. Findings showed that there is a positive relationship between marketing innovation strategy and sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.
2. The second null hypothesis also stated that process innovation strategy does not affect sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State. Findings revealed that Process innovation strategy significantly influences sales performance of food and beverage firms in Akwa Ibom State.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it is clear that adopting innovation strategies does improve sales performance. The researcher concluded that marketing innovation strategy and process innovation strategy are a key element of innovation strategies that influences sales performance in food and beverage companies.

Recommendations

The researcher made the following recommendations based on the findings:

1. Companies that have not been using marketing innovation and process innovation strategy to a large extent should do so to be competitive and enhance their sales performance.
2. More attention should be paid to emerging and modern technology as the world is bringing up new ways of doing almost everything.

REFERENCES

- Al-Battaineh, M.T.(2018) Effect of Innovation Strategies on The functional Performance of SMEs Organizations in (Hassan Industrial City), (7)5, 12-18
- Al-kalouti, J., Kumar, V., Kumar, N., Garza-Reyes, J. A., Upadhyay, A., & Zwiendelaar, J. B. (2020). Investigating innovation capability and organizational performance in service firms. Wiley, 103-113
- Azadegan, A., Napshin, S., & Oke, A. (2013). The influence of R&D partnerships on innovation in manufacturing firms: The moderating role of institutional attachment. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 33(3), 248-274
- Canh, N. T., Liem, N. T., Thu, P. A., & Khuong, N. V. (2019). The impact of innovation on the firm performance and corporate social responsibility of Vietnamese manufacturing firms. *Sustainability*, 1-14.
- Corniani M. (2008). Push and Pull Policy in Market-Driven Management. *SYMPHONYA Emerging Issues in Management* (1)5, 34-43
- Eke, C. U (2022). The Influence of Online Marketing on Marketing Performance of Small And Medium Scale Businesses in Akwa Ibom State Nigeria, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 05(01): 118-127
- Etuk, S., Udoh, I. S. and Udowong, E. C. (2021). Electronic Marketing and Marketing Performance Of Small And Medium Scale Enterprises in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 9(4): 1-17
- Freeman, C. (2004). Technological infrastructure and international competitiveness. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 13(3), 540-552
- Gakii, A. and Maina, S. (2019). Nexus between online marketing strategies and marketing performance: a critical review of related literature and research agenda. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 11(15): 99-107.
- Ifekanandu C. C., Renner B. A. (2024), Innovation Strategies and Sales Performance of Food and Beverages Firms in Rivers State. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Business Innovation* 7(1), 76- 89.
- Kenea, D. A (2020) The Role of Innovation Strategy in Improving Organizational Performance and Productivity: Focus on Heineken Beverage Industry, Ethiopia, *Annals of the University of Craiova for Journalism, Communication and Management*, (5)6, 31-56,
- Maier, A. (2014a), Cercetări și contribuții privind dezvoltarea modelelor de management al inovării, PhD thesis, Technical University of Cluj- Napoca, Romania
- Muita, J.K. (2013). Innovation strategies and competitive advantage in the Telecommunication industry in Kenya. *Repository Journal of University of Nairobi*. 3(2) 45-55.
- Rodriguez, C. C., Carrillat, F., & Jaramillo, F. (2004). A meta-analysis of the relationship between market orientation and business performance: evidence from five continents. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 21(2), 179-200.

Rogers, E. (1962) *Diffusions of innovations*. New York, Fress press, 87p.

Shih, T. (2018). Determinants of enterprises radical innovation and performance: Insights into strategic orientation of cultural and creative enterprises. *Sustainability*, 10(1), 1871-1884.

Tidd, J., and Bessant, J. (2018). *Managing innovation: Integrating technological, market and organizational change* (6th ed.). John Wiley & Sons